

Solvent Influences in the Reactions of Diols with HBr.

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Kinetics of reactions of ethylene glycol, propylene glycol and 1, 3-butandiol in acetic acid- CCl_4 , acetic acid-diphenylmethane and acid- CHCl_3 with HCl, HBr and HI is reported. The order of reactivity is $\text{HI} > \text{HBr} > \text{HCl}$. Solvent influences are rationalised on the basis of a positive ion-dipolar reaction.

In our previous communication¹, we reported the Arrhenius parameters for the reactions of glycols with HBr. The present communication deals with solvent effects on the reaction and also the differential effect of the three hydrogen halo acids.

Experimental

The solvents used, glacial acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, diphenyl methane and chloroform, were purified by the usual procedure and distilled. Substrates used were of guaranteed quality and distilled before use. Hydrogen halo acids used were freshly distilled azeotropic mixtures. The reactions were followed by the usual argentimetric procedure (Volhard's method)

The concentration of the diols was 0.05M, and those of HCl, HBr and HI were respectively 0.05M, 0.05M and 0.025M. The stoichiometry of the reactants in the reaction is 1:2 (Diol:HX), and the product is the alkyl halide. The reactions were followed till about 60% of the disappearance of halo acid, because they become very slow after this. The second order rate constants, calculated for the first step of the reaction, were reproducible to within 2-3% error.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants are given for the first step of the reaction of all the three glycols. The second order rate constants for the reactions of ethylene glycol, propylene glycol and 1,3-butandiol with HBr at 50° in pure acetic acid¹ are respectively 1.00, 0.687 and 0.040 l.mole⁻¹ min⁻¹.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS ($10^2 \times k$ l. MOLE⁻¹ MIN⁻¹) FOR REACTIONS BETWEEN DIOLS AND HCl AT 50°

Solvent	Acetic acid : CCl_4 :: 80:20% v/v	Acetic acid : Chloroform :: 80:20% v/v	Acetic acid : Diphenyl methane :: 80:20% v/v
Ethylene glycol	1.501	1.669	1.226
Propylene glycol	0.9677	0.9412	1.086
1,3-Butane diol	0.2600	0.2143	0.2222

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS $10 \times k$ l. MOLE⁻¹ MIN⁻¹) FOR REACTIONS BETWEEN DIOLS AND HBr AT 50°

Solvent	Acetic Acid : Carbon tetrachloride :: 80:20% v/v	Acetic acid : Chloroform :: 80:20%(v/v)	Acetic acid : Diphenyl methane :: 80:20% (v/v)
Ethylene glycol	8.333	8.572	10.47
Propylene glycol	5.000	5.000	6.667
1,3-Butane diol	0.3698	0.3999	0.4525

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k l. MOLE⁻¹ MIN⁻¹) FOR REACTIONS BETWEEN DIOLS AND HI 50°.

Solvent	Acetic acid : Carbon tetra- chloride :: 80:20% (v/v)	Acetic acid : Chloroform :: 80:20% (v/v)	Acetic acid : Diphenyl methane :: 80:20% (v/v)
Ethylene glycol	1.4000	1.0490	1.4780
Propylene glycol	1.2600	0.9495	1.2390
1,3-Butane diol	0.3572	0.3923	0.3328

It is evident from the tables that the rate process is dependent upon the nature of the nucleophile. The heavier members are more nucleophilic, largely because their atoms are more polarisable; the clouds of valence electrons about the atoms are most easily distorted by electrophilic centres. The more easily this electron cloud is distorted, the lower will be the activation energy of substitution. Along with this polarisability phenomenon, the ionisation potential^{2,3} and the solvation energy of the attacking nucleophiles are responsible factors to cause the relative nucleophilic order: $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$.

The differences in rates with the three halo acids can be rationalised, alternatively, as follows;

It is noted that the rate order follows the increase in acid strength of HX. If we write

$$\text{then } K = \frac{[\text{ROH}_2^+][\text{X}^-]}{[\text{ROH}][\text{HX}]}$$

$$\text{and } \text{rate} = k[\text{ROH}_2^+][\text{X}^-] = Kk[\text{ROH}][\text{HX}]$$

Therefore, $k_{\text{obs}} = K k$.

The values of k need not be very different (although this may not be very likely); so the rates need not reflect differences of nucleophilicity of X^- . On the

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other hand, the k values would surely differ for the three hydrogen halides in acetic acid (if only because of the low dielectric constant of this medium), and this could well be the most important feature of these reactions.

Solvent influences :

It is seen from the tables that the rate of substitution of the glycols in different solvent mixtures is almost the same, but between pure acetic acid and binary mixtures of acetic acids, the reaction rates are accelerated with a decrease in dielectric constant, D . This is a pointer to the nature of the reaction. As mentioned earlier, the reaction is a bimolecular displacement, of

which the initial step is the formation of a conjugate acid at the hydroxylic oxygen. The solvent effect, points to a positive ion-dipolar type of reaction which requires an increase in rate with decrease in D .

References

1. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and K. C. SAMANTRA, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 71.
2. E. S. GOULD, "*Inorganic Reaction and Structure*", Henry Holt & Col, New York, 1955, p. 207.
3. E. S. GOULD, "*Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry*", Holt, Rinehart & Winston, New York, 1965, p. 1063.